

Mar Coll's *Matar al padre / Killing the Father* (Movistar+: 2018): A Female
Auteur between Film and Television in Spain

Abstract: This article approaches the professional career of the Spanish screenwriter and director Mar Coll (Barcelona, 1981–), with special focus on what is her only television series so far, *Matar al Padre / Killing the Father* (2018). Trained at the prestigious Escola Superior de Cinema i Audiovisuals de Catalunya, Coll debuted in 2008 with the feature film *Tres dies amb la família* (*Three Days with the Family*), for which she won the Goya Award as Best New Director. After a second feature film in 2013, *Tots volem el millor per a ella* (*We All Want What's Best for Her*), Coll received an offer to develop a series for the pay-TV platform Movistar+, which sought to make an ambitious commitment to fiction series with a strong authorial imprint as part of a brand-building strategy. It was the first time that Coll, who until then had developed her career exclusively within the framework of the independence of *auteur* cinema, did a professional work for a media group. Studying the launch and reception of *Matar al padre*, the only one of the eight series released by Movistar+ during the 2017-2018 season directed by a woman, the text will ask about how female authorship is articulated and perceived in Spanish contemporary television,.

Keywords: television fiction, women filmmakers, Spanish cinema and television, television authorship, Mar Coll

Introduction: Female Authorship in Spanish Film and Television

On May 25, 2018, the pay-TV platform Movistar+ premiered the seventh series of its ambitious original fiction strategy, *Matar al padre* (*Killing the Father*). The four-episode series told the story of Jacobo Vidal (Gonzalo de Castro), a lawyer living in Barcelona and an obsessive and despotic father of teenagers Tomás (Marcel Borràs) and Valeria (Greta Fernández). A drama with comedy undertones, each episode of *Matar al padre* followed Jacobo during the years 1996, 2004, 2008, and 2012, portraying his problematic relationship with his own dying father, his soon-to-be ex-wife Isabel (Paulina García), and his children. With the passing of the years, Jacobo's behavior becomes more authoritarian and alienating, but at the end of a health scare, the effects of the

economic crisis and the birth of his first grandson make him have an epiphany over his existential vacuum.

Matar al padre was the first Movistar+ series directed by a woman and only the second with a female co-creator, after *Velvet Colección* (*The Velvet Collection*, 2017–). This fact did not go unnoticed in the press, and *Matar al padre* immediately became known as “the first series of Movistar+ with a feminine signature” (Güell 2017).¹ Making a series for a pay-TV platform such as Movistar+ was a worthy professional opportunity for Mar Coll, a respected *auteur* film director. Her first two features, the Catalan-language *Tres dies amb la família* / *Three Days with the Family* (2008) and *Tots volem el millor per a ella* / *We All Want What's Best for Her* (2013), confirmed her solid voice in Spanish cinema thanks to her naturalistic style and interest in showing female characters in uneasy family situations. Movistar+ hired for its first slate of fiction series a group of filmmakers who had no previous television experience or were essentially known for their film work, as was the case with Coll and other relevant directors, such as Alberto Rodríguez (*La isla mínima* / *Marshland*, 2014), Enrique Urbizu (*No habrá paz para los malvados* / *No Rest for the Wicked*, 2011), and Juan Cavestany (*Gente en sitios* / *People in Places*, 2013). After almost two decades of Spanish fiction basing its commercial power on a model where authorship was strongly blurred, in recent years a considerable effort has been made to give prominence to creators, to the point that the term “showrunner” (used in the United States to refer to the main person responsible for a series) has come to be used regularly in both industry and journalistic discourses in Spain. However, in this new visibility for television creators, the scarce presence of women is noticeable, as only a low number of women directors regularly work in television fiction.

In this context, *Matar al padre* becomes a privileged example to analyze how female creators suffer inequality in Spanish film and television. As commercial cinema gives few opportunities to women filmmakers, therefore it is in the most authorial and independent circuit where women creators such as

¹ “*Matar al padre*, la primera serie de Movistar+ con sello femenino.”

Mar Coll find their best opportunities. But Coll, whose work falls under the distinct trend of the “Other Spanish Cinema”, has a creative universe so personal and so removed from some conventions of television fiction that hindered the reception of *Matar al padre*, as evidenced by the virtual invisibility of the series after its premiere.

This article is based on the hypothesis that the current process of valorization of television authorship in Spain is perpetuating the inequality that makes it difficult for women gain relevant positions in the industry, especially as creators in projects with a distinctive creative vision. Further, television's interest in incorporating film professionals not only fails to solve the existing gender gap but also very likely widens it. To show the repercussions of this situation, this article has two main objectives. First, I will use Mar Coll's work as an exponent of the current situation of female filmmakers in Spain, and of the difficulties in consolidating their professional careers. The Spanish public grant system for cinema, as I will discuss later, has opted to promote a commercial cinema financed by large media groups where hardly any opportunities are given to women directors. That puts women directors on the margins of the system, where they try to protect their creative vision, but that also makes it difficult to consolidate their careers. So Mar Coll's decision to accept Movistar+'s offer to direct a series in the context of her previous career serves as an exponent of the complex professional decisions that women filmmakers must make in the new media landscape. But at the same time, the conditions of autonomy in which this project took place says a lot about her effort to keep her prestige and independence as filmmaker.

Second, I will analyze *Matar al padre* as an exponent of an original production strategy that has sought differentiation through an *auterist* style, focusing on the Mar Coll's creative autonomy and the somewhat disappointing public projection as a female creator in this context. For this second purpose, I will use recent approaches to television authorship with has stressed the prestige and brand-building qualities relevant contemporary fiction. In addition, although women film directors have received much attention in recent years—both from a historical (Nair and Gutiérrez-Albilla 2013; Zecchi 2014; Zurián

2015) and a specific contemporary perspective (Camí-Vela 2005; Núñez Domínguez, Silva, and Vera 2012; Zurián 2017)—research is still scarce on female television directors or women combining film and television fiction. This article tries to partially fill that gap using the trajectory of Mar Coll.

Female Film Directors in Spain: Deception, Promise and Life in the Margins

As stated in the previous section, in recent years research on Spanish female filmmakers has grown considerably, with many offerings ranging from the work of pioneers during the Republican period and the years of Franco's dictatorship to the work of directors born after the arrival of democracy in Spain. Precisely, until the early 90's only two women directors achieved a consistent body of work, Josefina Molina (1936–) and Pilar Miró (1940–1997). Both Molina and Miró were trained at the Official School of Cinema, and despite the difficulties, they used their years working in state-owned channel Televisión Española making anthology dramas and fiction series to gain experience and polish their professional skills. As the only two female director working steadily in Spanish cinema for many years, it is through their cinema that the introduction of a female gaze into Spanish cinema took place (Zecchi 2014, 88–111). Although in the case of Miró, her relationship with feminism and her own consideration as a creative woman was as complex as sometimes contradictory (see Martin-Márquez 1999, 141–180). Of course, during 60s and early 70s, female filmmakers such as Helena Lumbreras worked on “minor cinemas”, a term used to refer to militant, marginal or avant-garde practices. But as Prieto Souto has stated, women were never given more than a “secondary role” in the histories of these Spanish “minor cinemas” (2015, 124).

The number of women directors began to grow gradually after the arrival of democracy and particularly during the 90s, something favoured (although to what extent, it is debatable) by the renewal sought by public support for new films (De Miguel, Ituarte, and Aguirre 2010, 105-107). In a significant number of cases, female filmmakers have had to rely on other occupations complementary to film jobs: the periods between their films tended to be long, and that is when they were able to achieve a certain continuity. In 2006 a group of female

screenwriters and directors founded the association CIMA (Mujeres en Medios Audiovisual [Women in Audiovisual Media]), which has focused on highlighting the gender inequality in Spanish cinema. According to Barbara Zecchi, with the creation of CIMA, “female directors [can] finally speak of their experience as women, because they are women, supported also by data from the Women's Institute” (2009, 245).²

Given the considerable difficulty of making new movies, some women directors have found opportunities in television. In that effort, the barriers between the two media have been visible. On the one hand, film directors with a significant number of television credits (such as Gracia Querejeta, Belén Macías or Azucena Rodríguez) are only hired to direct individual episodes, without receiving much creative responsibility beyond that. On the other hand, the female television directors with the highest number of credits and responsibility as executive producers (Begoña Álvarez Rojas and Sandra Gallego) do not have film work. In this situation, many female film directors have opted for advertising or teaching (the Goya nominated Paula Ortiz, a PhD in Comparative Literature, is an example of both) as the preferable way of earning income while obtaining funding for their film projects. But precariousness is hard to beat. The public grant system makes possible a high number of films, but many of the them are never distributed or recoup their costs in commercial release, a structural problem in Spanish cinema (Jordan 2011: 19–23).

At the same time, there has been a growing trend in Spanish film culture “towards a quasi-celebration of marginality – in itself, a necessity – as an identity position.” (Kourelou, Liz, and Vidal 2014: 144). A relevant example of this identity based on being on the margins is the label “el Otro Cine Español” (“the Other Spanish Cinema”), used to describe the generation of filmmakers who debuted in the 2000s, with University training and aesthetic features ranging from “the auteur film tradition and European art film to instances connected to the evolution of experimental documentary film” (Palacio and

² “Las directoras hablan por fin de su experiencia como mujeres, por ser mujeres, respaldas además por datos del Instituto de la Mujer.”

Ibáñez 2015). They work with limited budgets (never above 2 million of euros per feature) and their movies are well-regarded in both national and international film festivals. “The Other Spanish Cinema” is a more a generation than a group, so there is not an “official” list of members. In 2013 the film magazine *Caimán*, which was originally created as the Spanish edition of *Cahiers du cinema*, published a list of 52 directors under this label. Of the eight women included, only Mar Coll, Neus Ballús and Cristina Diz had directed fiction films, with Coll as the sole exception in not having a documentary background (Caimán 2013).

The consolidation of this alternative cinema based on “otherness” and a “quasi-marginal” identity took place with the last reform of the state public film grants in 2016, where a “selective” call was introduced for documentaries, directorial debuts, movies with special cinematographic, social and cultural values, and experimental titles. The “general” call, oriented to movies with higher budgets produced by broadcasters (an obligation they have since 2004), presents substantial difficulties for female filmmakers: according to the 2018 CIMA report, in that year only two films directed by women were financed by commercial television channels, compared to none in 2017 (CIMA, 2019). As they are not normally offered jobs in commercial cinema or in television, the auterist/independent circuit is where the main chances are for women directors to continue their careers.

Mar Coll is a good example of how this financing dynamic reinforce the tendency of female filmmakers to work in the auterist/independent circuit. In the following pages, I will analyse the film trajectory of Mar Coll before going to television and the significant role that ESCAC, the film school where she was trained and it is now her main employer, is giving her both opportunities and some level of independence to create her *auteur* film work.

Mar Coll, Film and TV *Auteur*.

As I already mentioned, teaching has been the day job for female filmmakers, or at least a source of complementary income. It has been also the case of Mar Coll, head of the Directing Department of the Escola Superior de Cinema i

Audiovisuals de Catalunya (ESCAC). The birth of ESCAC in 1994 offered a platform for a new generation of Catalan film professionals, with a structure based on a combination of public support and media companies (Maixenchs 2006, 209–10), in a wider process of resurgence of Spanish film production (Wheeler 2014, 10). ESCAC has particularly focused on the external projection of its alumni. This has taken place especially through the associated production company Escándalo Films (ESCAC Films). In 2007, the program “Ópera Prima” was established; through the program, Escándalo Films produced the first films of its most promising graduates. For Aritz Lekuona, Marketing Director of ESCAC, the target was “to capture, nurture and promote talent”, so they can go from shorts to features (Allum 2016, 92). The status of women in the Escándalo Films is noteworthy. The first two films produced within the “Ópera Prima” program had female directors, *Lo mejor de mí* (*The Best of Me*, 2008) by Roser Aguilar and *Tres dies amb la família* by Mar Coll, followed by other titles, such as Elena Trapé’s *Blog* (2011), Liliana Torres’s *Family Tour* (2013), Denise Castro’s *Salvación* (*Salvation*, 2016), and Marta Díaz’s *Mi querida cofradía* (2017). In fact, of the 11 directors featured on the official ESCAC website as participants in the program, six are women.³

Mar Coll, born in Barcelona in 1981, enrolled at the ESCAC in 1999 to pursue a degree in film directing, graduating in 2003. Her final thesis project was *La última Polaroid* (*The Last Polaroid*, 2004), a 20-minute short-film about two teenage friends who spend their last hours together before one of them moves with her family to another city. *La última Polaroid* won various awards in Spain and at international festivals, making it easier for Mar Coll to make the leap to a feature debut, which she wrote with Valentina Viso, a Venezuelan screenwriter trained at the ECAM (Madrid Film School). *Tres dies amb la família* established Mar Coll’s creative universe: the exploration of family relationships within the Catalan bourgeoisie, this time about the three days that a young woman returning from studying abroad spends with her family after the death of her grandfather. After winning three prizes at the Malaga Film Festival, including as Best Director, the film received additional honors at the Saint Jordi and

³ Available at: <https://escac.com/opera-prima/>.

but as an evolution and, in that evolution, the reception of this film will influence the next one.” (Sánchez de la Nieta 2014).

Mar Coll struggled, however, to make a third film and returned to shorts films with *La inquilina / The Tenant* (2015). The relevance gained by *Tres días amb la família* granted her a job, but not as a filmmaker working steadily, but as lecturer and head of the Directing Department at ESCAC. Eight years after her first movie, filmmaking was a still a “hobby” for Mar Coll. *Matar al padre* was originally a script for a feature film that, in Coll's words, “was never going to receive money to be financed” (Bernal 2018).⁶ It was then that Coll was contacted by Movistar+ Head of Fiction Domingo Corral, who asked if she was interested in making a television series. With her frequent co-screenwriter Valentina Viso and Diego Vega, Coll expanded the feature-film script into the four-episode *Matar al padre*. Until then, Mar Coll hadn't considered working in television, as she thought that “the director there is a more technical figure, brings the knowledge about directing actors or where to put the camera but doesn't have control over the contents” (Bermejo, 2018).⁷ The creative freedom and the financing made her change her mind about a medium she had previously considered “hostile” (Bermejo, 2018). With the offer by Movistar+ to make a television series, Mar Coll was able to direct again, but following the TV *auteur* template.

The notion of *auteur* series establishes a complex framework for interpreting the production dynamics of television fiction. In the United States, the author's voice has been located on the figure of the writer-producer, who is mainly responsible for the program. Talking about that context, for Mittell, the differences between film and television authorship are based on the role performed in each case by the person mainly responsible for the project. In film, the director exerts *the authorship by responsibility*: the production system “vests responsibility for collective creativity in the singular authority of the director” (Mittell, 2015, 88). But in television, what is prevalent is an *authorship by*

⁶ “Era un proyecto que nunca iba a recibir dinero para ser financiado (...).”

⁷ “(...) el director es una figura más técnica, aporta sus conocimientos sobre dirigir actores o dónde poner la cámara pero no tiene el control sobre los contenidos.”

management, where “the producer rather than director is accorded the final responsibility for the choices that shape the finished work” (Mittell 2015, 88). But from a European perspective, this difference is not that simple because there has not always been such a strict separation between film and television. That model facilitated that films *auteurs* such as Ingmar Bergman, Rainer Werner Fassbinder, and Lars Von Trier worked for television. For many years and until the arrival of commercial networks, this model was also hegemonic in Spanish television fiction, where filmmakers made the most ambitious fiction projects launched by state-owned television (e.g., the literary adaptation *La forja de un rebelde*, directed by Mario Camus, had a budget of 14 million of euros, a figure not adjusted for inflation [Prados 1990]). The two most relevant Spanish female directors before the 1990s, the already mentioned Pilar Miró and Josefina Molina, spent the first part of their careers working for television (Vernon 2017). Although Miró barely returned to TV after establishing her film career, Josefina Molina directed titles such as the expensive biopic *Teresa de Jesús* (TVE1, 1984).

Therefore, Movistar+'s commitment to bringing film talent to television can be considered, in a sense, a return to the authorial tradition that allowed film directors such as Mario Camus and Josefina Molina to combine film project with television series. With the arrival of commercial broadcasters in the 90s, the model was no longer sustainable, as the new independent companies opted for producing more hours of content with lower budgets. Domingo Corral, Head of Fiction of Movistar+, called established filmmakers to ask them to make fiction series for the pay-TV platform, at the time devising a strategy to compete with new operators (such as Netflix) and strengthening its video-on-demand capabilities. Projects by Goya Award winners—such as Alberto Rodríguez (*La Peste / The Plague*, 2017–), Cesc Gay (*Félix / Félix*, 2018), and Enrique Urbizu (*Gigantes / Giants*, 2018–2019)—were quickly put into development and later greenlighted. One of the aspects that made it easier to attract this talent was a change in the production model, with series seasons having a reduced number of episodes (between 4 and 8, as opposed to the 13 of the series for the broadcast channels) and shorter in length (up to 60 minutes per episode, instead of the much-maligned standard of 70 minutes).

Mar Coll was the only female director working for Movistar+ to receive the go-ahead for a series during the first season, but Corral said this was not a factor in consideration: "When I personally called Mar Coll, it honestly didn't even cross my mind if it was a man or a woman. I just called her because I thought she was a great director and a great creator. I really wanted to bring Mar's world, so located in author circuits, closer to television, and therefore to the audience" (Caro 2018). No doubt that Mar Coll's selection for the first season of original fiction programming allowed Movistar+ to incorporate a female young talent representing the "Other Spanish Cinema", along with Juan Cavestany (co-creator of the comedy *Vergüenza*). Mar Coll's previous works were very different from the commercial genre cinema to which the movies of Enrique Urbizu or Alberto Rodríguez can be ascribed. In fact, of the six dramas released by Movistar+ in its first season, four (*La Zona*, *La Peste*, *Félix* and *El día de mañana*) were crime dramas. The only two dramas that deviated from this pattern were, strikingly, created by women: the romantic comedy *Velvet Colección* and the family drama *Matar al padre*. Given that, the relationship between genre and gender in Movistar+ production strategy is hard to question.

As already stated, Domingo Corral's call came when Coll was developing, together with Valentina Viso, the script for her third feature film: "It was a ninety-minute film designed with three episodes: two long ones and a final short one of fifteen minutes. There were also the time jumps" (Bernal 2018).⁸ Finally, this structure was adapted to four episodes, each taking place in a different year between 1996 and 2012, from the period after the Olympic Games of Barcelona to the worst years of the financial crisis that started in 2008. Some elements guaranteed that the continuity between *Matar al padre* and Mar Coll's previous works was total. From the point of view of production, she was responsible for directing the four episodes of the series, which she wrote with her usual collaborator Valentina Viso and Diego Vega. Viso's participation is especially important; in Coll's words: "The two films and the

⁸ "Era una peli de noventa minutos que estaba pensada en tres episodios: dos largos y un cortito final de quince minutos. También estaban los saltos temporales."

series could perfectly well be a trilogy about family. Maybe it's because I write with my best friend, Valentina Viso, whom I've known since I was ten. We are like sisters" (Bernal 2018).⁹ The setting of the series in Catalan bourgeois family life was a key element connecting *Tres dies amb la família* and *Tots volem el millor per a ella* with *Matar al padre*. *Matar al padre* was produced by Escándalo Films in what was the first television work for the company (which by then was using the ESCAC Films label more frequently). Sergi Casamitjana, ESCAC director and producer of Coll's previous work, was the executive producer of *Matar al padre*, along with Domingo Corral, Ismael Calleja, and Fran Araujo of Movistar+. In *Matar al padre*, Coll also worked with collaborators from her previous works, such as production designer Xènia Besora, script Belén Funes, camera operator Gina Ferrer, casting director Mireia Juárez, editor Aina Calleja, and composer Maik Maier. The continuity between *Matar al padre* and Coll's films and shorts is absolute, as she (except for the episodic structure and male main character, which were part of the original project) did not make any concessions to an established television formula and kept all of her narrative, thematic and aesthetic traits. The main exception is use of the Catalan language, something that can be attributed the lack of presence of the co-official language in the programming produced for the national channels. I must stress that Coll was vocal in letting known that she only accepted after getting reassurances about the creative freedom she was going to enjoy and her independence safeguarded: "At first I was very cautious with Movistar+'s offer. There was a discourse of author series, risky, thinking of other audiences, respecting the processes and the times... And the truth is that they have delivered" (Bernal 2018).¹⁰ Therefore, it not far-reaching to conclude that never in the recent history of Spanish fiction television has a female creator been able to control a project as Mar Coll, as director and screenwriter, did with *Matar al padre*.

9 "Las dos pelis y la serie podría ser, perfectamente, una trilogía sobre la familia. A lo mejor es porque escribo con mi mejor amiga, Valentina Viso, a la que conozco desde los diez años. Somos como hermanas."

10 Original Spanish text: "Al principio fui muy cautelosa con la propuesta de Movistar +. Había un discurso de series de autor, arriesgadas, pensando en otros públicos, respetando los procesos y los tiempos... Y, la verdad, es que han cumplido."

Mar Coll and the Complexities of Female TV Authorism

In this section, I will approach Mar Coll's construction as a television author as part of Movistar+'s broader strategies to promote its series as prestigious content. To do that, it is useful to deal first with some consideration about the role of the showrunner. Although the concept belongs to the North American context, I bring it up because it has served to redefine an approach to television authorship and its use has expanded to other markets, such as Spain. But it is not an isolated case, as research shows in the case of the France (Redvall, 2013) and France (Rochant 2017). Movistar+ has frequently presented the creative head for its series as "showrunner", although in many cases they do not conform to the writer-producer American model: the film director Enrique Urbizu was an extreme case, presenting himself in interviews as showrunner of *Gigantes* (2018–2019), even though he was neither a writer nor a producer (see, as example, Murillo 2018). As more and more "the showrunner functions as a translator of cultural capital into economic capital (Blakey 2017, 329), television creators with prestige as filmmakers (such as Urbizu and Coll) are brand-building elements even more relevant than the performers.

Thus, it seems clear that, in television, the creator is no longer just a professional figure, but also a discursive one. At the presentation of the service Movistar Series in December 2014, in which Domingo Corral announced the start of the original fiction strategy, he had already formulated the principles behind the project, stating that he was looking at "identity" traits, "choosing very good creators and that they have a lot of freedom to take risks," and prioritizing stories "commanded by characters" and with an "aesthetic priority" (Fórmula TV 2014).¹¹ The central position these directors acquired for the Movistar+ brand was apparent in the way in which the series were introduced to the audience, identifying "the author" in all the promotional elements (including posters for outdoor advertising) with the credit "created by" or "a series by." For *Matar al padre*, the authorship of the series was highlighted in two ways. On the one

¹¹ "Entre sus rasgos 'identidad,' 'escoger a creadores muy buenos y que tengan mucha libertad para arriesgar,' historias donde 'lo que mande sea el personaje' y haya una 'prioridad estética.'"

hand, the creation credit was attributed to Coll, Valentina Viso, and Diego Vega in the promotional materials and posters. However, in the titles and credits there was not, as is usual, a distinction between “created by” and “written by.” Instead, Coll, as well as Viso and Vega, appear in a single credit of “creado por” (notably, in masculine form even though “series” is a feminine noun in Spanish) immediately before Mar Coll's credit as director. This way, a unique case for Movistar+ series, *Matar al padre*, was presented as a cohesive entity. In the promotional materials, Mar Coll sometimes received a separate credit as director, which reinforced the relevance given by Movistar+ to the prestige of her film work.

Movistar+ has mainly used film festivals to launch its original series, a way to associate this new slate of programming with the prestige of cinema. In their critique of the excesses of television authorship, Newman and Levine explained that the “status of television as art is an effect produced through the elevation of certain instances of television over others, thereby legitimating not just the television texts at hand but also the efforts and tastes of those who create and consume them” (2012, 57). To achieve this “elevation” of Movistar+ series, *La Peste* and *Vergüenza* were presented at the San Sebastian Film Festival in September 2017, and *Gigantes* and *Arde Madrid* at the same festival a year later. In October 2017, the thriller *La Zona* debuted at the Sitges Film Festival, which specializes in horror and fantasy films. In the case of *Matar al padre*, it had a double presentation at film festivals taking place in the spring of 2018. First, *Matar al padre* was screened in April as part of the section Málaga Premier at the Málaga Film Festival, which specializes in Spanish and Latin American movies. The edition is remembered because all the main awards were won by female ESCAC alumni. As film journalists Pepa Blanes and María Guerra (2018) wrote in their chronicle, the women of the ESCAC became “empowered” at the Málaga Film Festival. A few days later, *Matar al padre* was presented at the D'A Film Festival of Barcelona, an event specifically focused on *auteur* cinema and where Mar Coll's very distinct creative universe had a fitting accommodation.

During the Málaga premiere, it became clear that the fact that *Matar al padre* was the first and only Movistar+ series by a female filmmaker was going to play a central role for the series reception. In fact, this aspect was highlighted in the different chronicles of the Malaga Festival. In an interview with journalist Javier Zurro from digital newspaper *El Español*, Coll acknowledged that it was “representative of the bad situation that exists” and pointed out the need to have “a plural culture that represents society, and therefore we have to have more relevance in creation” (Zurro 2018).¹² The conversation around *Matar al padre* as the sole female *auteur* series by Movistar+ intensified during series promotional period in anticipation of its premier on May 25. Mar Coll kept using this fact as a way to denounce the gender inequality in Spanish cinema: “The truth is that I see it as a worrying fact. That, from 8 to 10 commissioned series, only one is directed by a woman is a reflection of the situation in the film industry. 10% to 15% of the films that are released are directed by women” (Martín-Lunas 2018).¹³ However, the main star of the series, actor Gonzalo de Castro, was much more critical when he addressed this question in a press interview: “We seem to have won an Oscar, but we should be ashamed that this happens in the situation we are at” (Moreno 2018).¹⁴ That Mar Coll was at the time the sole Movistar+ female creator was a determining factor even during the shooting (see the already mentioned Güell, 2018), and, later, the reviews of the series emphasized the gender of the creator/director: “Women take 'control' of Movistar fiction”¹⁵ for *El Mundo* (Pérez 2018), while in *El País*, *Matar al padre* was “a feminine look at the paternal figure”¹⁶ (Marcos 2018), maybe a kind of unappreciative way to reference the series (particularly, by a female journalist). Additionally, because of a sensitivity belonging to *auteur* cinema, *Matar al padre* did not connect with mainstream television criticism. The only exception was Paula Hergar, reviewer for the specialized portal Vertele, who considered the

12 Original Spanish text: “Significativo de la mala situación que hay” and “Necesitamos una cultura plural que represente a la sociedad, y por tanto tenemos que tener más peso en la creación.”

13 “La verdad que lo vivo como un dato preocupante. Que de 8 a 10 series encargadas haya sólo una dirigida por una mujer es el reflejo de la situación de la industria cinematográfica. Un 10 o un 15% de las películas que se estrenan están dirigidas por mujeres.”

14 “Parece que hemos ganado un Oscar, pero debería darnos vergüenza que pase esto en el momento en el que estamos.”

15 “La mujer toma el 'control' de la ficción de Movistar.”

16 “*Matar al padre*, una mirada femenina a la figura paterna.”

series “one of the most soulful made by Movistar+”¹⁷ (2018). In fact, the most positive review for *Matar al padre* came from a film journalist, Luis Martínez, writing for the newspaper *El Mundo*, for whom the series was “the last miracle of which television has been capable of”¹⁸ (2018). When, at the presentation of the new season in September 2018, the president of Movistar+, Sergio Oslé, showed a ranking of its original series in relation to non-original series on the platform, *Matar al padre* was the only one of the eight original series absent from the list (Onieva 2018). The only series by a female creator had also been Movistar+’s biggest failure.

Conclusions

The results of Movistar+ strategy of original fiction illustrate how, as Newman and Levine have recognized, the cultural elevation of television is “as much a masculinization as it is a refinement of the medium’s class status” (2012, 10) . When Movistar+ approached film directors to create its new slate of original fictions, the company reproduced the gender inequality on which Spanish cinema rests. This fact was acknowledged by Domingo Corral, Movistar+’s head of fiction: “At the launch of this project, I can tell you quite frankly that we have not stopped to think about quotas or if we have to have X women. Our goal is to create quality products from an industry that already existed, and that is certainly much more populated by men than women” (Caro 2018).¹⁹ Later Movistar+ fulfilled Domingo Corral's promise to produce more series led by women, but these projects have highlighted a fact that should not go unnoticed: Anna R. Costa (*Arde Madrid / Burn Madrid Burn*), Teresa Fernandez-Valdéz (*Instinto / Instinct*), and Esther Martínez Lobato (*El embarcadero / The Pier*) are married to the co-creators of their series on Movistar+. Although creative couples made up of real-life couples are common in both film and television, their frequency in the Spanish television context seems to indicate that, as a result of the *machismo* installed in the industry,

17 “(...) una de las producciones con más alma de las que ha hecho Movistar+.”

18 “(...) el último milagro del que ha sido capaz la televisión.”

19 “En el lanzamiento de este proyecto te puedo decir con toda franqueza que no nos hemos parado a pensar en cuotas o si tenemos que tener X mujeres. Nuestro objetivo es crear productos de calidad a partir de una industria que ya existía, y que ciertamente está mucho más poblada por hombres que por mujeres.”

many women do not get the go-ahead for their projects unless they are co-led by men. In an interview months after the premiere of feminist comedy *Arde Madrid*, Anna R. Costa (a working screenwriter before marrying actor and director Paco León) Costa responded to a question about whether she had felt discriminated against during the presentation events for the series talking about she “felt part of the background all the time” (Martinez 2019).²⁰

None of the other women directors of "The Other Spanish Cinema" has created a fiction series, so *Matar al padre* remains an isolated experience in relation to how television can be a space of opportunity for females filmmakers working on the margins of independent cinema in Spain. But it doesn't mean that there are no lessons to be drawn. Mar Coll has not been the only member of "the Other Spanish Cinema" to direct for Movistar+, although she was the one who kept her creative identity in stricter terms. With *Vergüenza* Juan Cavestany, working with veteran television director Álvaro Fernández Armero, shaped an unconventional comedy for the Spanish context, but with the recognized influence of television creators such as Ricky Gervais and Larry David. Asked if she had felt more freedom in relation to her film work, Coll replied, “Not more free, because despite the mentality of working with authors that this network has, it is finally a network. What it does give you is a lot of peace of mind, because the adventure of directing a film in this country is impossible” (Bernal 2018).²¹ What Coll refers to is the difficulty of getting financing to make her third feature film. In one of the interviews from the Málaga Film Festival, this time part of a report about the presence of female filmmakers in the programming, Coll again connected her role as the only Movistar+ female *auteur* to the situation of women in Spanish cinema and reminded the ESCAC experience: “When a film school becomes a producer, it not only acts as a bridge between training and professional life but also helps things start to

20 “Me he sentido todo el tiempo en un segundo plano. Muchas veces, en los 'junkets' de entrevistas estábamos los dos, y solo parecían interesar sus declaraciones. Solo me entrevistaron para una publicación.”

21 “Más libre tampoco, porque a pesar de la mentalidad de trabajar con autores que tiene esta cadena, finalmente es una cadena. Lo que sí que te da es muchísima tranquilidad, porque la aventura de dirigir una película en este país es imposible.”

change” (Llopart 2018, 68).²² It was the ESCAC, and not Movistar+, that was really taking chances on female filmmakers.

From Coll, Movistar+ took the prestige of a respected filmmaker, no matter the number of viewers for the series. But the failure of *Matar al padre* has been a warning sign, as this brand-building strategy placed Mar Coll's work in a position of critical dissonance: it is no coincidence that *Matar al padre* was vindicated by a film critic who knew the movies she made under the umbrella of the “Other Spanish Cinema”, while it was ignored or vilified by television reviewers. An unintended result of the experience has been associating female authorship in prestige television drama in Spain with failure. Working in a context where professional continuity for women directors is difficult to achieve, Mar Coll boldly ventured into television and accepted this risk. But neither for the heightened public profile that Movistar+ offered nor for the work opportunity she gained, Coll was willing to trade her independence and offered with *Matar al padre* piece that utterly embodied her creative vision.

Bibliography:

- Allum, Stefanie. 2016. “The New Catalan Cinema: Regional/National Film Production in a Globalised Context.” PhD diss., Northumbria University. Accessed December 27, 2018. <http://nrl.northumbria.ac.uk/36248/>
- Benavente, Fran, and Glòria Salvadó Corretger. 2011. “Ficcions possibles: imatges del cinema català dels darrers deu anys.” Report, Observatori de Producció Audiovisual, Universitat Pompeu Fabra. Accessed December 20, 2018. <http://hdl.handle.net/10230/32584>
- Bernal, Fernando. 2018. “Mar Coll, directora de *Matar al padre*: “Quería acabar con los arquetipos de género.” *El País*, May 4. Accessed December 27, 2018. <https://smoda.elpais.com/placeres/mar-coll-directora-de-matar-al-padre-queria-acabar-con-los-arquetipos-de-genero/>

²² “Cuando una escuela de cine se convierte en productora, no sólo ejerce de puente entre la formación y la vida profesional sino que también contribuye a que las cosas empiecen a cambiar.”

Blakey, Elisabeth. 2017. "Showrunner as Auteur: Bridging the Culture/Economy Binary in Digital Hollywood." *Open Cultural Studies* 1 (1): 321–332. doi: 10.1515/culture-2017-0029

Blanes, Pepa, and María Guerra. 2018. "Las mujeres de la ESCAC se empoderan en Málaga." *Cadena SER*, April 23. Accessed December 20, 2018. https://cadenaser.com/programa/2018/04/17/la_script/1523961566_156649.htm

!

Caimán. 2015. "Los nombres de este nuevo / otro cine español." *Caimán*, August 30. Accessed August 14, 2019. <https://www.caimanediciones.es/los-nombres-de-este-nuevo-otro-cine-espanol/>

Camí-Vela, María. 2005. *Mujeres detrás de la cámara: Entrevistas con cineastas españolas (1990-2004)*. Madrid: Ocho y Medio.

Caro, Alfonso. 2018. "Nombres propios: Domingo Corral." *El Palomitrón*, April 26. Accessed December 27, 2018. <https://elpalomitron.com/nombres-propios-domingo-corral/>

CIMA. 2019. "Informe CIMA 2018. La representatividad de las mujeres en el sector cinematográfico." Accessed July 3, 2019. https://cimamujerescineastas.es/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/INFORME_ANUAL_CIMA_2018.pdf

De Miguel, Casilda, Ituarte, Leire, and Aguirre, Katitxa Aguirre. 2010. "Women Directors in Spanish Cinema, 1995-2005." In *Feminist Challenges in the Social Sciences: Gender Studies in the Basque Country*, edited by Mari Luz Esteban y Mila Amurrio, 105–107. Reno: Center for Basque Studies / University of Nevada.

Filmin. 2009. "Entrevista a Mar Coll, directora de *Tres días con la familia*." *Blog Filmin*, July 2. Accessed June 15, 2019. <https://www.filmin.es/blog/entrevista-a-mar-coll-directora-de-tres-dias-con-la-familia>

Fórmula TV. 2014. "Domingo Corral: 'Nuestro plan es producir ficción para Movistar Series, vamos a empezar en breve a desarrollarlas'." *Fórmula TV*, December 10. Accessed December 23, 2018. <https://www.formulatv.com/noticias/42460/domingo-corral-nuestro-plan-producir-ficcionmovistar-series/>

Gente en sitios/People in Places. 2013. Directed by Juan Cavestany. Spain: Apaches Entertainment.

Güell, María. 2017. "Matar al padre, la primera serie de Movistar+ con sello femenino." *ABC*, November 17. Accessed December 20, 2018. https://www.abc.es/play/series/noticias/abci-matar-padre-primera-serie-movistar-sello-femenino-201711170037_noticia.html

Hergar, Paula. 2018. "Matar al padre, la versión cruda de *Los Simpson* en Movistar." *Vertele*, May 22. Accessed December 20, 2018. http://vertele.eldiario.es/noticias/Matar-Movistar-podria-version-Simpson_0_2012798701.html

Jordan, Barry. 2011. "Audiences, Film Culture, Public Subsidies: The End of Spanish Cinema." In *Spain on Screen. Developments in Contemporary Spanish Cinema*, edited by Ann Davies, 19–40. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.

Kourelou, Olga, Liz, Mariana, and Vidal, Belén. 2014. "Crisis and Creativity: The New Cinemas of Portugal, Greece and Spain." *New Cinemas: Journal of Contemporary Film* 12 (1-2): 133-151. doi: 10.1386/ncin.12.1-2.133_1
133

La isla minimal/Marshland. 2014. Film. Directed by Alberto Rodríguez. Spain: Atípica Films/Atresmedia Cine. <https://www.lavanguardia.com/gente/20181114/452927922650/leticia-dolera-aina-clotet-embarazo-polemica-dejate-llevar-serie.html>

Llopart, Salvador. 2018. "Málaga, cine en femenino plural." *La Vanguardia*, April, 15: 64–65.

Maixenchs, Josep. 2006. "A Look at Film Training in Catalonia." *Quaderns del CAC* 23-24: 207–10.

Marcos, Natalia. 2018. "Matar al padre, una mirada femenina a la figura paterna." *El País*, May 24. Accessed December 20, 2018. https://elpais.com/cultura/2018/05/24/television/1527163239_975527.html

Martín-Lunas, Milagros. 2018. "Matar al padre o la historia de un fracaso." *El Independiente*, May 25. Accessed December 20, 2018. <https://www.elindependiente.com/tendencias/2018/05/25/matar-al-padre-serie/>

Martinez, Beatriz. 2019. "Anna R. Costa: 'Ha llegado el momento de las mujeres y tenemos que estar a la altura'." *El Periódico*, January 26. Accessed January 27, 2019. <https://www.elperiodico.com/es/mas->

periodico/20190126/anna-r-costa-ha-llegado-momento-mujeres-tenemos-estar-altura-arde-madrid-series-feminismo-7264962

Martin-Márquez, Susan. 1999. *Feminist Discourse and Spanish Cinema: Sight Unseen*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Martínez, Luis. 2018. "Todas las muertes de todos los padres." *El Mundo*, April 22. Accessed December 20, 2018. <https://www.elmundo.es/papel/firmas/2018/04/22/5adb3b1122601d88148b4655.html>

Mittell, Jason. 2015. *Complex TV: The Poetics of Contemporary Television Storytelling*. New York: NYU Press.

Moreno, Adriano. 2018. "Gonzalo de Castro: 'La tele ha involucionado, ahora hay un cachondeo de cojones'." *Cadena SER*, May 24. Accessed December 20, 2018. https://cadenaser.com/ser/2018/05/24/television/1527157548_405994.html

Nair, Parvati, and Julian Daniel Gutierrez-Albilla, eds. 2013. *Hispanic and Lusophone Women Filmmakers: Theory, Practice and Difference*. Manchester: Manchester University Press.

Newman, Michael Z., and Elana Levine. 2012. *Legitimizing Television: Media Convergence and Cultural Status*. New York: Routledge.

Murillo, Silvia. 2018. "Enrique Urbizu: 'Me he sentido muy libre por lo descabellado y temerario del guion'." *El Telégrafo*, October 8. Accessed June 15, 2019.

<https://www.eltelegrafo.com.ec/noticias/cultura/1/enrique-urbizu-entrevista-cultura>

No habrá paz para los malvados/No Rest for the Wicked. 2011. Directed by Enrique Urbizu. Spain: Lazona Films/Telecinco Cinema.

Núñez Domínguez, Trinidad, May Silva, and Teresa Vera. 2012. *Directoras de cine español. Ayer, hoy y mañana, mostrando talentos*. Sevilla: Universidad de Sevilla / Fundación Audiovisual de Andalucía.

Onieva, Álvaro. 2018. "Movistar+ desvela la audiencia de sus series propias (y podemos sacar varias conclusiones)." *Fotogramas*, September 12. Accessed December 27, 2018. <https://www.fotogramas.es/series-tv-noticias/a23097097/audiencia-series-originalesmovistar-conclusiones/>

Palacio, Manuel, and Ibáñez, Juan Carlos. 2015. "A New Model for Spanish Cinema. Authorship and Globalization: the Films of Javier Rebollo." *Journal of Spanish Cultural Studies* 16 (1), 29-43. doi:

Pérez, Pedro L. 2018. "La mujer toma el 'control' de la ficción de Movistar." *El Mundo*, May 25. Accessed December 20, 2018. <https://www.elmundo.es/television/2018/05/25/5b06b65d46163f39148b4580.html>

Prados, Luis. 1990. "TVE estrena la serie *La forja de un rebelde*, la producción más ambiciosa de su historia." *El País*, March 30. Accessed August 12, 2019. https://elpais.com/diario/1990/03/30/radiotv/638748005_850215.html

Prieto Souto, Xose. 2015. "Margins and Absences: Women in Spanish Minor Cinemas". In: *A New Gaze. Women Creators of Film and Television in Democratic Spain*, edited by Concepción Cascajosa, 115-125. Newcastle upon Tyne: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.

Redvall, Eva Novrup. 2013. "A European Take on the Showrunner? Danish Television Drama Production." In: *Behind the Screen: Inside European Production Cultures*, edited by Petr Szczepanik and Patrick Vonderau, 153–169. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.

Rochant, Éric. 2017. "Naissance d'un showrunner français ou l'art de produire des séries TV." *Le journal de l'école de Paris du management* 127 (5), 21–27.

Sánchez de la Nieta, Ana. 2013. "Entrevista: Mar Coll, directora de *Todos queremos lo mejor para ella*." *Fila Siete*, November 4. Accessed June 15, 2019. <https://filasiete.com/noticias/entrevistas-protagonistas/entrevista-mar-coll-directora-de-todos-queremos-lo-mejor-para-ella/>

Tots volem el millor per a ella/We All Want What's Best for Her. 2013. Film. Directed by Mar Coll. Spain: Escándalo Film.

Tres dies amb la família/Three Days with the Family. 2009. Film. Directed by Mar Coll. Spain: Escándalo Film.

Vernon, Kathleen M. 2017. "Screening Room: Spanish Women Filmmakers View the Transition." In *Women's Narrative and Film in 20th Century Spain*, edited by Kathleen Glenn, 95–113. New York: Routledge.

Wheeler, Duncan. 2014. "Spanish Films, 1992–2012: Two Decades of Cinematic Production and Critical Discourse." In *(Re)viewing Creative, Critical*

and Commercial Practices in Contemporary Spanish Cinema, edited by Duncan Wheeler and Fernando Canet, 7–34. Bristol: Intellect.

Wheeler, Duncan. 2016. "The (Post-)feminist Condition: Women Filmmakers in Spain." *Feminist Media Studies* 16 (6): 1057–1077.

Zecchi, Barbara. 2009. "Desde el 'cine de mujeres' a CIMA: ¿hacia un nuevo discurso fílmico femenino?" *Boletín Hispano Helvético* 13–14: 243–260.

Zecchi, Barbara. 2014. *Desenfocadas. Cineastas españolas y discursos de género*. Barcelona: Icaria

Zurián, Francisco A. ed. 2015. *Construyendo una mirada propia: mujeres directoras en el cine español*. Madrid: Síntesis.

Zurián, Francisco A. ed. 2017. *Miradas de mujer cineastas españolas para el siglo XXI (del 2000 al 2015)*. Madrid: Editorial Fundamentos.

Zurro, Javier. 2018. "El sueño húmedo de Freud: la crisis del macho español." *El Español*, April 18. Accessed December 20, 2018.

https://www.elespanol.com/cultura/cine/20180418/sueno-humedo-freud-crisis-macho-espanol/300720519_0.html